

UNC PROJECT LABORATORY STUDY BRIEF

CABMILK STUDY Study Info Sheet

Updated: August 13, 2025

Study contact: (For critical values, other study issues): Dr Mphatso Kantonya, 0994 622 253

Contact for billing: Dr Clifford G Banda; Email: cgbanda@mlw.mw
Dr Mphatso Kantonya; Email: mkantonya@mlw.mw
Prof David Lissauer; Email: dlissauer@mlw.mw

Study Lab Point Person: James Kaphatika/Sandress Lupunga

Study duration: 18 Months

Target enrollment/location : 100 Mother/Infant pairs (Area 18 and Kawale Health Centres).

Study synopsis: Breastmilk transfer of cabotegravir and its association with infant safety outcomes in a sub population of Malawian lactating mothers on cabotegravir for HIV PrEP in Blantyre and Lilongwe: An observational pharmacokinetic study.

Study issues: Long-acting injectable cabotegravir (CAB-LA) is a novel antiretroviral agent recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) for pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) to prevent HIV acquisition. While CAB-LA is highly effective in preventing HIV, its safety profile during breastfeeding has not been well established. There is limited evidence on the extent of cabotegravir transfer into breastmilk and its potential impact on breastfed infants, particularly in sub-Saharan African settings where CAB-LA is being rapidly rolled out as it is being done under PATH-TO-SCALE in Malawi.

The CABMILK study is an observational pharmacokinetic cohort study designed to evaluate the transfer of CAB-LA into breastmilk and its presence in the circulation of exposed infants. The study will enrol up to 25 lactating, HIV-negative mothers who are receiving CAB-LA for PrEP, along with their breastfeeding infants aged 0 to 4 months and follow them up for 8 months. Maternal plasma, breastmilk, and infant dried blood spot (DBS) samples will be collected at defined timepoints over a four-week period following administration of 4 CAB-LA doses from enrolment

Samples will be analyzed using high-sensitivity LC-MS/MS to determine cabotegravir concentrations. The study will also monitor infant clinical outcomes and developmental milestones to assess potential safety signals associated with drug exposure.

Findings from this study will fill a critical evidence gap in the use of CAB-LA during lactation, guiding national and global policy for PrEP implementation among breast feeding populations. Results will be shared with study participants, policymakers, WHO, the ethics committee (NHSRC), and disseminated through peer-reviewed publications.

1. See attached specimen collection and processing sheet (or add details below if minimal processing required).

2. LIS Considerations:

- Clinician Name: Mphatso Kantonya
- Study Name: CABMILK STUDY
- Patient ID: CAB-A-001/ CAB-A-001-INF

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- First Name: CABMILK
- Last name: CABMILK

Storage

LDMS Considerations

1. LDMS/Storage Considerations: This study will be stored in the LDMS under an internal group using the same procedures as used for network studies. Note that all aliquots made should be stored in the **filled by lab** boxes.
 - a. Group: Internal
 - b. ID1: CAB-A-001; CAB-A-001-INF
 - c. ID2: CABMILK STUDY
 - d. ID3: Leave it blank
 - e. Date: dd/mmm/yyyy
 - f. Visit: 1; 2;10
 - g. Visit unit: Visit/PK
 - h. OPID: Leave it blank
 - i. CLINIC: Leave it blank

LABORATORY SCHEDULE OF EVENTS AND SPECIMEN PROCESSING

NOTE: Blood and Breast Milk sample will be collected from Mothers at visit 5 and 7 while DBS samples from infants will be collected on visits 5 through 9.

Visit	LIS Visit Code	Sample Tubes	Department	Tests
Visit #	Visit #: 5....10 Visit unit: Visit/PK	• DBS (INF) • 5 mL EDTA tube (M) • 5 mL breast milk (M)	CPL	Dry and store at room temperature in a ziplok bag with desiccant.
			CPL	Store 2 aliquots @2mL of Plasma @-80 degrees
			CPL	Store 2 aliquots @2mL of Breast Milk @-80 degrees

Site Investigator

Name: Dr Mphatso Kantonya

Signature:

Date: 13 August 2025

Laboratory Manager (or delegate)

Name: Manley Kamija

Signature:

Date: 13 August 2025